

NOTABLE PROBLEMS CONFRONTING THE EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF THE FRENCH LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The teaching and learning of the French language in Nigeria continue to face persistent structural, pedagogical, and sociolinguistic challenges despite the country's strategic position among several francophone neighbors and its active membership in the ECOWAS. All nations pitched by nature as the neighbors of Nigeria are francophones. Niger and Tchad to the north, Cameroon to the east, Benin to the west and bordered by the Atlantic Ocean to the south. French is one of the most widely used international languages in commerce, scientific and technological research, administration, education, literature, etc. Therefore, the need for French in Nigeria therefore, cannot be overemphasized. Nigerians need the knowledge of the French language to effectively interact with francophone countries locally and internationally and; be able to attend international seminars and conferences without any problem. Nigeria's geographical, economic, and diplomatic as well as her educational and religious needs make it imperative for her to give adequate attention to learning French. However, its teaching and learning in Nigeria are not without problems. This paper highlights these constraints and argues that meaningful reform-through teacher training, resource provision, policy enforcement, and adopting learner centered methodologies is essential for improving FLE in Nigeria. Addressing these problems will strengthen multilingual competence, promote regional cooperation, and enhance Nigeria's socioeconomic and diplomatic engagement within the francophone world.

Introduction

The Linguistic Situation in Nigeria.

It will be necessary to briefly examine the linguistic situation in Nigeria as the contextual background to this study. Nigeria is reputed to be Africa's most multilingual nation. Oyetade (2004, p.3) quotes SIL (2003) and

states that “the most recent authoritative inventory puts the number at 515, with more than 8 dead and several others undergoing different types of endangerments”. This means that up to 20% of African languages are spoken in Nigeria. However, this picture of diversity becomes blurred with the existence of the three principal or main languages: Hausa in the north, Igbo in the southeast and Yoruba in the southwest. These are the dominant languages of Nigeria owing to the numerical strength of their speakers. As a result of this factor, some recognition has been accorded them in the 1979 and 1999 Constitutions of Nigeria; as well as in the 1977 National policy on Education, which has been revised in 1981, 1998, and 2004 respectively.

In addition to the numerous indigenous languages, the official language of Nigeria is English. It is the single most important language in Nigeria as its influence looms large in all spheres of endeavor in Nigeria. It is the language of administration from the local government level to the federal level, even if the state is monolingual. It is the language of education, commerce and industry, the judiciary, and the language of debate in federal and states legislative houses. This role as a language of upward social mobility and personal aggrandizement has conferred upon it a prestigious status, which makes some people think it is the best and only language to use in our nation. Its role as a lingua franca has made it a unifying force in Nigeria. This is why in the national language debate, some people always suggest English as a possible candidate for that role due to the intense and explosive ethnic rivalry in Nigeria. Therefore, unlike indigenous languages, the English language is highly preserved and favored in the educational system.

The French language was introduced to the Nigerian educational system as far back as the nineteenth century. The precise date when the 1st lesson in French occurred in Nigeria has not been discovered by the researchers. The language is taught as a school subject in some prestigious nursery, primary, and secondary schools. In tertiary institutions, it is mainly studied as a foreign language. French came as a foreign language and has remained a foreign language ever since. The attitude towards it is somewhat ambivalent. However, in 1996, the fortune of French in Nigeria changed when the former Head of State of Nigeria, Late General Sanni Abacha, declared the new status of French as the nation’s second official language in 1998, and this was stated in section 1, no. 10 of the National Policy on Education. Apart from the issue of geographical location, various researchers have discussed different reasons why the French language is important to Nigerians, and the Nigerian have been discussed by various researchers and the Nigeria French Institute in Abuja was included in the discussion. The Institute opines that the French language is very important for Nigerians because:

- a) Learning one language is insufficient: In today’s world, speaking one foreign language is insufficient. Students who speak several languages will increase their chances of finding a job, whether at home or abroad. Learning another language enriches the mind and opens up new personal and professional horizons.
- b). Along with English, French is the only language spoken on all five continents. More than 220 million people on all five continents. French is a major international communication. It is the second most widely learned language after English and the sixth most widely spoken in the world. French is also the second most widely taught language after English and, is taught on every continent. The OIF, an international organization of French-speaking countries, comprises 77 member states and governments. France also operates the largest international network of cultural institutes, which run French-language courses for close to one million learners.
- c). A career asset: The ability to speak both French and English is an advantage for finding a job with many multinational companies using French as their working language in, a wide range of sectors (retailing, automotive, luxury goods, aeronautics, etc.). France, as the world’s fifth-largest economy, attracts entrepreneurs, researchers and the top foreign students.
- d). an introduction to an incomparable cultural universe: France is often considered the language of culture. A French lesson is a cultural journey into the worlds of fashion, gastronomy, the arts, architecture, and science.

Learning French also offers access to the original text of the works of great French writers such as Victor Hugo or Marcel Proust and famous poets like Charles Baudelaire or Jacques Prévert. It means being able to hear the voices of actors Alain Delon or Juliette Binoche, and the pleasure of being able to understand the words of French songs sung by an Édith Piaf or a Charles Aznavour and even sing them yourself.

e). An advantage for studying in France: Speaking French opens up opportunities for higher education at some of France's best-known universities (the Sorbonne, Pierre Marie Curie University, etc.) or elite *grandes écoles* (HEC, Polytechnique, ESSEC), often on very favorable financial terms. Students with a good level of French may be eligible to apply for a French government grant to enroll on a postgraduate course of their choice in France, leading to an internationally recognized postgraduate degree.

f. The language of international relations: French is both a working language and an official language of the United Nations, the European Union, UNESCO, NATO, the International Olympic Committee, the International Red Cross, and international courts. French proficiency is essential for anyone considering a career in any international organization.

g). A language that opens up the world: After English and German, French is the third most widely used language on the Internet, ahead of Spanish. An ability to understand French offers an alternative view of the world through communication with French speakers from all over the world and news from the leading international French-language media (TV5, France 24 and Radio France Internationale).

h) A language for learning other languages: French is a good grounding for learning other languages, especially Romance languages (Spanish, Italian, Portuguese, and Romanian) and even English, since over half of modern-day English vocabulary is derived from French.

i) A high standard of teaching: French teachers are renowned for their dynamic, inventive approach and high expectations Ajiboye (2003, p. 6). Because French has a reputation for excellence, students tend to be highly motivated and attain a high level of proficiency. France also plays an active role in providing in-service training for French teachers abroad so that the courses delivered are always of a high standard.

j) Many exchange opportunities: Students can easily make contact with French speakers of their own age, as pen pals or via the Internet. There are different exchange programs in France that offer rewarding experiences. Thousands of French schools are twinned with counterparts around the world, creating links with the world's largest educational network.

Despite these numerous advantages, the teaching and learning of the language in Nigeria is not without problems.

French Language

According to the RealFrench.net website accessed 20th August, 2016), French owes its existence to some ancient languages. These include:

- Gaulish is - the language of the Celtic people (of which the fictional Asterix the Gaul was one) who inhabited primarily the territory of what is now modern day France prior to the Roman invasions.
- Latin, the language of the invading Romans.
- Frankish, the language of the Germanic people who occupied this territory after the fall of the Roman Empire and, who gave France its name.
- Old Norse, the language of the Vikings, occupied many of the coastal and in-land navigable areas of Northern France before being granted the area now known as Normandy (meaning "Land of the Norsemen").

The RealFrench.net website affirms that from around Louis XIV to the beginning of the 20th century, French was viewed as the language of international communities within European and European-influenced countries.

This situation probably arose from a number of factors, including the consistent political power that France enjoyed during this time, its geographical position at the heart of Europe, its strong historical relations with all the major Western nations, and its immense cultural prestige, both in terms of the arts and in terms of “cultured living” (food, wine, fashion, furniture, etc.) aspects that were important to the diplomatic set. It was also established by the RealFrench. The French language was adopted as the official language of France in 1539 (through the special linguistic decree referred to as **Villers-Cotterêts**, passed by François Ier).

The RealFrench.net website also submits that of, the nearly 50 million French speakers outside of Europe, the greatest proportion is found in Central and West Africa, where French is the official language in many cases. The highest concentration of French speakers is found in the Maghreb (Algerian, Moroccan, and Tunisian), although many speakers are also found in countries such as Benin, Ivory Coast, Cameroon, Senegal, Zaïre, Togo, Congo, Burkina Faso, and Mali. In the Indian Ocean, there are significant numbers of French speakers in Madagascar, Mauritius, and Réunion (a Département d’Outre Mer or DOM, meaning that it is administered like a metropolitan département).

It is the second most widely learned language after English and the second most widely taught language after English.

From the site² La; francophonie dans le monde, it was discovered that:

- ❖ 128 million francophones: fluently speak French as a native or adopted language and use it on a regular basis.
- ❖ Seventy two million ‘partial’ francophones: live in a francophone country but do not speak French regularly due, to limited knowledge.
- ❖ 100-110 million students of all ages: do not live in a francophone country but have learned or are learning French to communicate with francophone.

French belongs to the enviable club of 12 of the world’s 5440 languages spoken by more than 100 million international organizations, including the United Nations (UN) and its agencies, in which the knowledge of French is a sine qua non for employment and plays the role of a most indispensable medium of communication for official transactions. It is also a fact that more than a third of the delegates of all the UN members at the General Assembly are French speaking. Moreover, French is one of the working languages in many international organizations, including: North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the African Union (AU), Amnesty International (AI), Médecins Sans Frontiers (doctors without borders), and the World Trade Organization etc. Together with English and Arabic, it is one of the languages of the Islamic Conference and the Arab League.

Furthermore, within the ECOWAS countries, French is the official language of 8 of the 15 member countries of ECOWAS (after the exit of Mauritania in December 1999). It is also the official language of 24 of all 53 African countries, including the eight of the ECOWAS.

According to a demographic projection by the Université Laval and the Réseau Démographique de l’Agence Universitaire de la Francophonie, French speakers will number approximately 500 million people in 2025 and 650 million people, or approximately 7% of the world’s population, by 2050. Estimates in 2013 suggest that the number of French speakers will reach 1 billion by 2060. (Free encyclopedia Wikipedia).

Nigeria and the French Language

Nigeria, as one of the countries in the world, cannot afford to be an island to herself. She needs to relate with her neighbors and other developed francophone countries in the areas of bilateral and international trade,

² [www.google.com/La francophonie dans le monde](http://www.google.com/La%20francophonie%20dans%20le%20monde), accessed 28 october, 2015

technological advancement, politics, international relations, tourism, etc. The use of the English language alone can never yield the desired results, and here comes the relevance of the French language in Nigeria. However, Osisanwo (2003, p. 17) opines:

In these days of global economic advancement, Nigeria must interact with other countries. Whether she likes it or not, with all her neighbors in the area of bilateral trade. Nigeria cannot be an island to herself when it comes to international trade out when it comes to international trade outside the West Africa sub-region. She cannot sit on the fence. Therefore, the knowledge of English alone may not be adequate. Therefore, every official representing the country on the platform of international trade must be fully equipped with the ability to communicate effectively in English and French.

Apart from the trade issue, Osisanwo (ibid) adds that

The world is in the age of computer technology, which has transformed the whole world into a global village. If Nigeria wants to derive maximum benefits from this technological advancement, reliance on the English language alone may not hasten the attainment of the desired goal. French nations are not lagging behind in the ongoing technological breakthroughs.

Ade-Ojo (2003, p. 3) also submits that Nigerians must pay more attention to the French language for proper understanding, cordial relationships, reciprocal and rewarding socioeconomic rapport, enduring political entente, exemplary multilateral relations, and transnational mobility, which are completely devoid of jealousy, suspicions, and conflicts and are rooted in the vision of achieving complete regional integration between all the countries of the West African sub-region.

Afolabi and Ajayi (2003, p. 48) add that studying French could lead to various jobs including the most interesting, challenging, and lucrative ones. These job opportunities could be found in banks, breweries, shipping industries, broadcasting, publishing, firms, the army, diplomatic service, civil service, air-ports, and external affairs. Therefore, the economic value of the French language can be seen areas where employers need people who have some knowledge of French. Therefore, Nigerians' ability to effectively use it would open up ample job opportunities in different companies both within and outside the country.

Despite these numerous benefits, the teaching and learning of this language face different challenges in Nigeria. Some of them are as follows:

(a) Government policy: One of the potent weapons against French studies in Nigeria is the government's decision to shovel French into the category of elective subjects in the secondary school curriculum many years ago. The decision dealt a devastating blow to the enthusiasm for French studies. However, in 1998, the policy was revised. The Nigerian government has considered it wise to raise the status of French from its former poor rating, which had reduced the language to a non-vocational elective in the secondary school curriculum. On December 14, 1996, in a speech at the Nigerian Institute for International Affairs, the late Nigerian Head of State, General Sani Abacha, said, "*Nigeria is resolutely launching a program of national language training that permit our country to become thoroughly bilingual in a short order.*" General Abacha's pronouncements and decisions finally led to the recognition of French as a second official language and made it compulsory in schools. Therefore, the third edition of the National Policy on Education, published in 1998, states, on page 9 thus:

For smooth interaction with our neighbors, it is desirable for every Nigerian to speak French. Accordingly, French shall be the second official language in Nigeria, and compulsory in schools.

According to Ajiboye (2003, p. 3), the revision was merely nothing but a feeble echo of the lost past. "*Asọ kò bo omóye mó, omóye ti rin ihòhò d'òjà.*" (Beautiful Omoye had strolled naked up to the market place; running up to clothe her was a wasted effort.)

(b) Inadequate Government support and commitment: Although French is officially recognized as Nigeria's second official language and a vital tool for regional integration, trade, diplomacy, and cross-border communication, its implementation in schools has not met policy expectations. Government at the Federal and State levels are not committed to the teaching and learning of the subject in schools. For instance, the above policy stated that French should be compulsory in schools. How serious is the government about it? Has it been fully implemented? What is happening to its teaching and learning in our primary, secondary and tertiary institutions since the policy was formulated over 20 years ago? Has it become a compulsory subject in schools? What is affecting its implementation? Is the policy not just a political statement or merely window dressing?

(c) Acute shortage of qualified and professionally trained teachers: This remains one of the most critical barriers to effective FLE in Nigeria and has far-reaching consequences for both teaching quality and learner achievement. There are many primary and secondary schools, particularly in rural and underserved areas, lack specialist French teachers. Both the Federal and State Governments failed to employ qualified French teachers into schools (primary and secondary) where a good foundation in French could be laid. One of the most effective ways to arouse students' interest in a subject is by making adequate provision for highly qualified and motivated teachers. The teacher is the heart and the cornerstone of any educational system. is the teacher. Whether at the primary, secondary, or higher institutions, the teacher is and will continue to be both the major indicator and the major determinant of quality instruction in schools. According to Ajiboye (2003:6) "*the teacher is a martyr to cultural discussion; hired to carry light into dark places.*" Afolabi and Ajayi (2003, p. 50), citing Fafunwa (1972), opines, "*the services of the teachers are to a nation, for they, more than any other professional group influence the lives of the Nigerian youths and therefore the nation's future.*" How adequate are French teachers in Nigerian schools in terms of quantity and quality? How prepared are teachers for the challenges of the French syllabus in schools? Are they satisfied with their jobs? Some principals even compounded this problem. Some of them do not encourage language teaching in their schools. In some secondary schools, the few available French teachers are saddled with heavy teaching load. In fact, in some schools, you find French graduates teaching entirely different subjects, such as social studies, Christian religious studies, and English language. That is not of their choice and out of compulsion since few students offer French in such schools. An overburdened teacher would definitely produce a job of lower quality.

(d) Insufficient Funding: Funding for the teaching and learning of the French language in Nigeria is another major challenge confronting the effective teaching and learning of the French in Nigeria. Adequate financial resources are essential for providing instructional materials, modern language laboratories, audio-visual aids, and updated textbooks that support language learning in communicative and interactive environment. Schools need money to sponsor French teachers to attend workshops, seminars, national and international conferences on French language development. The government should sponsor French students for acculturation program outside the country. The shifting of the locus of immersion program from France and French West Africans countries. To Nigeria French Language Village is not the best option for French students who need to be competent and fluent in the language. The local alternative, NFLV, established in 1991, has not really got its environmental furniture. Ajiboye (2003:5) submits "*... as a credible alternative to the French Year Abroad, the Institution of a local apparatus in a multi-ethnic, anglophone setting is at best like seeking to get out of a tunnel with the flicker of a dying cigarette*". If the government shows more commitment to the teaching and learning of French in schools through adequate funding and provision of modern learning resources, the morale of both teachers and students will be boosted.

(e). Lack of Instructional Resources for French Teaching: It is obvious that effective teaching and learning of French in schools depends greatly on the availability and adequacy of instructional resources. In most of the

schools where French is offered, there are no French Resource centers equipped with different tools ranging from elementary improvised devices to highly complex and sophisticated machines specially designed to help French teachers cope with specific teaching needs and situations. These resources include modern French books and other printed materials, pictures, displays, models, computers, televisions, tape recorders, video tapes, audio tapes, filmstrips, and other audio visual materials and equipment that can be used to stimulate, attract, and compel students' attention during French lessons in schools.

(f). Poor Home Support: The first people with whom the child comes in contact are his/her parents, who initiate him/her into the societal cultural norms and values. In Nigeria, parents and guardians prioritize other subjects that they consider more economically rewarding, thereby reducing students' interest and motivation in French. Parents are increasingly showing keen interest in the subjects offered by their children and wards in secondary schools. Quite often, they show preference for science and commercial subjects as they want their children and wards to become engineers, medical doctors, accountants, business managers, and so on, regardless of the students' ability to pursue such commercial and science courses. The parents and guardians are completely ignorant of the numerous benefits of learning the French language, especially in terms of various job opportunities. Some parents will even buy recommended textbooks on mathematics and other science subjects and shun their children whenever they request for money to buy the recommended French textbooks which that they offer in the school along with other subjects. This parental attitude is sufficient to discourage the students from offering French at the senior secondary school level.

(g). Social class background and school effects: These have a lot to do with children's acquisition of the French language. Arogundade (2003, p.56) states that *"it is a known fact that because of poor conditions in many public schools (primary and secondary schools), the more affluent parents often send their children to fee-paying private schools (primary/secondary and tertiary institutions). These children perform well enough in the schools. Lindsay (1973, p.3) emphasized that the difficulties besetting the child's path depend on the parents, teachers, and education authorities"*. It has also been asserted that teachers avoid teaching in rural schools because they believe that the provision of equipment and language laboratory (including French) is poor and that governmental policy decisions favor urban schools. Trained and well qualified teachers prefer to live and work in the urban areas. All these have effects on the education of the child, including second language acquisition, especially the French language.

Conclusion

This paper discusses some notable problems confronting the teaching and learning of the French language in Nigeria. If nothing is done to address these issues, the pronouncement of the late former head of state as touching making the French language a second official language of Nigeria will be taken as a mere window dressing. Since there are numerous benefits to having French knowledge, as discussed in our paper, the government should be ready to offer solutions to the issues raised. Drastic efforts must be put in place to tackle the challenges confronting the learning of the French language in Nigeria.

Recommendation

a). Adequate Government Support: The federal and state government of Nigeria should be ready to give adequate support to the teaching and learning of French. The government should come out with plans to make the study of the language more fundamental so that students would no longer see the study of the language as a mere academic exercise for examination.

✓ By sponsoring French language teachers for workshop, Seminar, National and International Conferences on French language development. The government can also sponsor French student in tertiary institutions for acculturation program. This is practicable in Nigeria if our Governments at all levels are

committed. Students studying French in Tertiary Institutions in Ghana were sponsored for their acculturation programme at Benin Republic and France. The government should be ready to make French language subventions available in Institution of higher learning in Nigeria.

✓ If the government shows more commitment to the teaching and learning of French in schools through adequate funding and provision of modern learning resources, this will boost the morale of students in the subject.

✓ Recruitment of more foreign and local French language teachers to our primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. All French teachers in schools should be inspired through some incentives, such as service training sponsorship within and outside the country, with the aim of improving the skills and teaching competences of French teachers of French.

✓ The dictum of ‘catch them young’ for French should be well embraced and incorporated into the Universal Basic Education. As a matter of policy, all public and private nursery schools should be encouraged to establish French language associations.

✓ Federal and State Radio and Television Stations should be mobilized to effectively teach and popularize the French language in the media. Moreover, all states should fully cooperate with the Federal Government in sponsoring knowledgeable persons to meetings where matters concerning the French language are discussed.

✓ Various modern French teaching and learning equipment and audio-visual materials should be procured in large quantities for schools, by the government.

✓ The government should encourage indigenous authors to publish books in the French for all levels of education in Nigeria. Such publications should contain idioms and should be subsidized by the government to reduce production cost and eventually sell to French students.

✓ **b). Immersion Program:** This is another issue that needs urgent attention if government wants students to learn French the way it should be learned. The immersion program of French students at Nigeria French Language Village may never be the best for French students. It could be reconsidered by the Nigerian government. French students must be competent in all areas necessary and restricting them to NFLV has not been a good alternative since its inception. If French students are going to France or any West African country where French is used as the official language for their immersion program where they will be exposed to these conventional expressions and will be able to achieve the desired competence in both written and oral language. Their translation will not be difficult. Taking students to the Benin Republic for an excursion on week-ends by the Nigeria French Language Village may not be adequate. It is not enough. The author of this paper had been there in 1995 as a student, and the normal practice of students was known. However, it was written on the walls and other places that “ici on parle français,” i.e., we speak French here. It is obvious that students conversed in their mother tongues in their hostels because nothing challenged or forced them to speak the language except for a few. However if they were taken to francophone countries for a year there would be a lot of difference because they would be forced to learn and speak the language at all costs.

Ajiboye (2003:5) submits: to achieve the desired competence in the language, the best option is for the students to live, albeit temporarily, with the owners or, native/constant users. This option is ultimately, not, as costly as it appears on the surface level, especially when we consider the amount of progressive damage that a less than equivalent could cause to true competence to true competence. He adds ...if we want to know what we have missed by choosing a purely local alternative (French Language Village at Badagry), ask your students, if we want to know what we could have gained by insisting on the year abroad being irreplaceable with a poorly funded local initiative, and ask those who had the true Francophone exposure.” If we want to know what makes a foreign language tick, ask students of German, Russian, and Portuguese.

c) Parent/Public Support: Parents should encourage their children to study the language because it is needed. Necessary incentives, motivations, encouragement, and materials needed by the children should be provided. They should take their children to a good school where the language is being taught.

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